

A CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH TO EMOTIONS AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

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The classical view of emotions posits that there are a few “basic emotions” that have specific fingerprints (neural circuitry, facial expressions, etc) and that they are either triggered directly by stimuli in the environment or by automatic appraisals of the stimuli. However, there is a growing body of research in support of the constructivist theory of emotion. This theory suggests that emotions traditionally labeled as *anger*, *fear*, *happiness*, *disgust*, and *sadness* are based on basic psychological processes (perceptual, attentional, and mnemonic systems) that combine in various ways to produce emotional and affective states, while these psychological “ingredients” may not themselves be specific to emotion. The purpose of this paper is to review the constructivist theory and some practical implications for child-rearing, education, autism interventions, and psychotherapy.

Keywords: emotions, affect, allostasis, constructivist, concepts.

INTRODUCTION

The science of emotion dates back to the year 1855, since then many theories of emotion have been formulated (Gendron & Barrett, 2009). Although scientists studying emotion have yet to reach a theoretical consensus, most of the theories of emotion recognize some common aspects or components of an emotional episode: a) a cognitive aspect; b) a feeling aspect (the emotional experience), c) a motivational aspect (action tendencies, action readiness); d) a somatic aspect (central and peripheral physiological responses); and e) a motor aspect which refers to overt behavior (Moors, 2009).

The theories of emotion have traditionally been divided into two dichotomous categories: basic emotion theory and appraisal theory (Gendron & Barrett, 2009). The basic emotion models assume that a few basic emotions exist, often five emotions are described, although not all theorists agree with this number. The five emotions are anger, fear, sadness, disgust, and happiness (Ekman, 2016). People

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from any part of the world can mostly correctly choose the emotion label when showed a corresponding facial expression. For example, people can choose the label fear when shown a face of a person acting scared (Ekman, 1972). Emotions are considered to be either hardwired into the brain from birth or to develop shortly after. According to this theory, each of these emotions has a particular bodily activation, experience, facial expression, behavior pattern, and neural circuit. The basic emotions are thought to be automatically triggered by events in the environment. Basic emotions theories recognize the variability in emotional responding and look at cultural norms or cognitive processing to account for this variability (Gendron & Barrett, 2009).

According to appraisal models, emotions are not triggered by objects or events in the world, instead, they are elicited by evaluations of events (appraisals). This theory explains why in the same situation different individuals or even the same individual at different times can experience a different emotion. For example, the death of a parent and the birth of a child, seemingly opposed types of events, can both cause sadness. Appraisal theorists propose that all events to which the same appraisal pattern is assigned will evoke the same emotion with its characteristic facial expressions and action tendencies. Most appraisal models assume that appraisals often occur effortlessly, and automatically generate emotions. However, given that they are cognitive in nature, appraisals can be directed effortfully – if a person is scared “automatically” when he/she hears a lion roar, that person can think that the lion is in a cage and that he/she is safe and therefore evoke a different kind of emotion, for example, calm (Roseman, 2001).

Weather events trigger emotions or appraisals of the events evoke the emotions, most theorists from the two models agree with the existence of some basic emotions as types of natural kinds. There is a third theory, however, that contests the existence of basic emotions and proposes a different paradigm (Barrett, 2006a). This third theory, with historical roots as old as the other two, is the psychological constructivist theory. Dunlap (1932) argued that, given the variability of bodily responses within an emotion category, emotion labels do not correspond to precise psychological entities. A prominent representative of the constructivist approach, Lisa Feldman Barrett (2006b) states that “People experience an emotion when they conceptualize an instance of affective feeling. In this view, the experience of emotion is an act of categorization, guided by embodied knowledge about emotion.” The constructivist literature has produced the Circumplex Map of Emotions, which proposes the existence of core affects, as states that influence reflexes, perception, cognition, and behavior. These core affects have internal and/or external causes, but humans do not have direct access to the causal connections (Russell, 2003). Within the circumplex model, emotions are plotted along two continuums: arousal and valence. Arousal describes physiological activation (brain activity) or autonomic responses

(tension, heart rate, muscle tension, sweating). Valence describes the positive or negative affect of emotions. For example, calm would be a positive low arousal emotion, while upset would be a negative high arousal emotion, according to this model (Kuppens, Tuerlinckx, Russell, & Barrett, 2013; Russell, 2003).

The new categorization of theories of emotion proposed by constructivists is divided into two major approaches: a) the classical view of emotion that includes basic emotion theories and causal appraisal theories, and b) the constructivist view of emotion that includes social construction theories, descriptive appraisal theories, psychological construction theories, neuroconstructive and rational constructivist theories as well as the theory of constructed emotion (Siegel *et al.*, 2018). The purpose of this article is to present the key features of constructivist theories of emotion and to explore some practical implications of the modern constructivist approach.

THE CONSTRUCTIVIST THEORY – TOWARDS A NEW SCIENCE OF EMOTION

“Basic emotion” theorists believe that anger, fear, happiness, and so on are discrete emotions and that each has dedicated brain circuitry (Ekman, 1992). In light of this belief, studies on emotion have largely focused on finding specific “fingerprints” (neural correlates) for each of the basic emotions. However, current evidence does not support this view. The constructivist approach proposes a new paradigm for the scientific study of emotion. This new paradigm posits that emotions traditionally labeled as anger, fear, happiness, disgust, and sadness are based on basic psychological processes (perceptual, attentional, and mnemonic systems) that combine in various ways to produce emotional and affective states, while these psychological “ingredients” may not themselves be specific to emotion (Kober, Barrett, Joseph, Bliss-Moreau, Lindquist, Wager, 2008). The results of a quantitative meta-analysis conducted by Kober *et al.* (2008) of 162 neuroimaging studies of emotion suggest that core limbic activation is associated more closely to medial frontal areas than their lateral counterparts and that the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex may play an essential role in the cognitive generation of emotional states. According to these results, a constructivist approach is considered by the authors the most sensitive at this point.

According to the constructivist Conceptual Act Theory (CAT), emotions emerge from representations of the body’s internal state (interoception) and exteroceptive representations of the current context, as causal indicators, as well as attention and conceptual knowledge about emotion categories, that was acquired via prior experiences. See Figure 1 for a visual representation of this model (MacCormack & Lindquist, 2017). Therefore, in the constructivist view, the emotional experience is not the basis for bodily changes as portrayed by the classical view, it is instead the last piece of the experiential “puzzle”.

Fig. 1. Emotion experience construction, according to CAT.

Allotaxis is a process at the core of the constructivist theories. According to the theory of constructed emotion (TCE) the primary purpose of the brain is to regulate all the physiological resources required to meet the immediate needs of the organism for action and learning, in the short term, and for survival, growth and reproduction, on the long run. It is more efficient for the brain to anticipate the bodily needs than to wait for the need to manifest itself and then to initiate action to satisfy that need. Allotaxis is defined as the process of predictively managing energy needs. Resource acquisition, allocation, and utilization are the activities of allostatic regulation and all of them are posited to operate on a predictive basis to enhance metabolic efficiency. From a constructivist view, mental processes such as emotion, cognition, perception, are predictive and under the constraints of allotaxis. In order for the brain to effectively regulate the body in the world, it runs an internal model of that body in the world (Fridman *et al.*, 2019; Barrett, 2017a).

Degeneracy is another key aspect of the theory of constructed emotions. Rather than being viewed as a single organ, the brain can be conceptualized as a massive network of high complexity. This complexity is possible through “degeneracy” which is defined as the capacity for dissimilar representations (different sets of neurons) to produce instances of the same category of emotion (e.g. happiness) in the same context. For the science of emotion, degeneracy means that it is unlikely that all instances of a certain emotion (e.g. anger) share a recognizable autonomic pattern (Barrett, 2017a).

Barrett hypothesizes that when the brain encounters new sensory input it prepares multiple competing simulations, using past experiences, to discover what the new sensory input is most similar to. Simulation is a pattern that is partially completed and that can categorize sensory signals to guide action in favor of allostasis. “Prediction errors” (unanticipated information from the environment – including the body’s internal milieu) functions as feedback for embodied simulations (“bottom-up” signals). The brain also infers the likely causes of motor and visceromotor actions while modulating them to deal with upcoming sensory events. The brain implements its internal model with concepts. These concepts categorize sensations to give them meaning. Predictions are concepts and completed predictions are categorizations that manage physiological regulation, guide action, and construct perception. Therefore, constructivist theories are skeptical of classical theories stimulus-response approach because they propose that meaning results from an action (predictive coding), perception follows the action and not the other way around (Barrett, 2017a; Barrett, 2017b).

In the constructivist view there are no basic emotions, instead, using population thinking, emotions are considered to be divided into categories. Each category of emotion (e.g. happiness) incorporates a population of highly variable, situated instances. So, an emotion is not a “natural kind” with firm boundaries, instead, it is a category of instances best suited to the current requests of the environment. An instance of happiness can feel differently depending on context. Also, the actions that a person takes when feeling happy are highly context-bound, are functional at the moment, they serve a purpose in the present based on past experiences. Likewise, the changes in the autonomic nervous system will vary across instances of happiness. Therefore, in the constructivist approach, no Platonic essence is assumed in an emotion category. Humans establish and reinforce emotion categories interactively to co-regulate each other (Barrett 2006, 2017a, 2017b, Hoemann *et al.*, 2020).

Constructivists acknowledge that certain facial expressions are associated with certain categories of emotion, however, they consider the classical pictures of facial expressions used by classical theories in their experiments as stereotypes rather than prototypes of that category. When feeling happy a person can laugh, smile, cry or have other facial expressions. In Western cultures, when feeling angry people scowl approximately 30% of the time, meaning that they make other moves with their faces about 70% of the time (Barrett, 2020). A scowl may serve as an expression of anger, humor, concentration or just a plea for assistance (Hoemann *et al.*, 2019).

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONSTRUCTIVIST THEORIES

Implications for emotional development

The learning environment of infants is full of multimodal cues that have high variability. To make sensory input meaningful (both from the outside world and from inside the body) the brain tries to find similarities. Therefore, an

infant's task is to learn which events are functionally similar and which are distinct, a task that may sound simpler than it actually is, given that little guidance is provided by perceptual similarities (Hoemann *et al.*, 2019). Constructivists hypothesize that words are a powerful "tool" that infants use to learn context-dependent, conceptual categories whose exemplars share mostly abstract similarities (Gelman & Roberts, 2017). According to this view, in the first two years of life, children develop emotion concepts by attending to emotion labels used by their caregivers when referring to their own emotions (e.g. "I'm very angry right now") and to the affective states of the children themselves (e.g. "You threw the toy, you seem angry"). Emotion concepts would therefore develop through the same mechanisms as the other concepts that children acquire. Given that emotions are considered by constructivists not to be "natural kinds", there is no perceiver-independent truth when labeling children's emotions, there isn't an emotion that is "there", inside the child, and that the parent observes and labels correctly or incorrectly. However, emotion categories can be described as sharing similarities in their contextual functional features. Collective intentionality establishes these similarities and they are reinforced via language. In conclusion, there is no right or wrong way to feel, the child constructs emotional experiences influenced by the culture. People from different cultures might experience a very different emotion in the same situation (e.g. when given an award someone might feel proud and someone else might feel embarrassed) depending on cultural values (e.g. individual achievement vs. collective harmony) (Hoemann *et al.*, 2019).

Implications for education

In light of the new science of emotion, educational books, games, and even movies (e.g. the very popular *Inside Out*) could shift from the classical view that holds that emotions just happen inside us and that there are a few basic emotions, and every instance of a certain "basic emotion" is the same as other instances of that emotion and different from instances of other emotions. Efforts to design evidence-based educational resources for children are in progress. An example of this process is the RULER – an evidence-based approach to teaching emotional intelligence (EI) and social emotional learning (SEL) to children. Central to this approach is the Mood Meter which is based on the Circumplex Map of Emotions with its two dimensions: pleasantness (valence) and energy (arousal). Children first learn to identify how they feel by choosing a corresponding color from the 4 quadrants (red: high energy-unpleasantness; blue: low energy – unpleasantness; yellow: high energy-pleasantness; green: low energy-pleasantness), then they develop emotional granularity by learning multiple emotion labels that fit in every quadrant and they learn emotion regulation skills (for a complete presentation see Nathanson *et al.*, 2016).

Implications for persons diagnosed with autism spectrum condition (ASC)

In the scientific literature addressing autism spectrum condition, a topic often investigated is emotion recognition. Results from a meta-analysis including data from 48 studies show that there is an emotion recognition difficulty in autism. The authors included in the meta-analysis studies based on the classical view of emotions: they used the 6 basic emotions approach (happiness, anger, fear, sadness, disgust, and surprise) and they inferred emotion recognition from the ability to “read” the correct emotion from faces or bodies either by labeling, matching or a different task (Uljarevic & Hamilton, 2013). When trying to teach people with ASC emotion recognition skills, the classical approach is also the one of choice (Baron-Cohen *et al.*, 2009). From a constructivist perspective, emotion recognition is based on an essentialist assumption as previously discussed in this article, instead, constructivists propose the term emotion perception (Barrett *et al.*, 2011). Research shows that context is encoded during emotion perception and those facial expressions when viewed in isolation might not be sufficient for perceiving emotion (Aviezer *et al.*, 2017; Barrett & Kensinger, 2010). By becoming knowledgeable in the new science of emotion, scientists studying ASC, as well as practitioners, could better understand and serve people with this condition.

Implications for psychotherapy

In her book, Lisa Feldman Barrett (2017c) tells the story of her husband going to a psychiatrist while he was going through a difficult time in his life. The man (Dan) scowled and knitted his brow and the psychiatrist immediately made the statement that he was feeling “pent-up anger”. Even though the client assured that he was not feeling angry the psychiatrist was so sure of his ability to “read” emotions from facial expressions, that Dan left the session. Maybe not everyone would have reacted in the same way. In a similar situation some people might agree with the professional and, thanks to the theory of constructed emotion, we know that those persons might even start to feel angry at that moment and also to interpret a state that was formerly conceptualized as “concentration” as an instance of anger. We have no way of actually “knowing” what a person is feeling (Barrett 2020, 2017a) and psychiatrists and psychotherapists could adopt this humble and also curious attitude while contributing to people’s wellbeing.

Besides the classical theory of emotions, another commonly held belief among many mental health professionals is the model of the triune brain, according to which newer brain structures were added over older ones. In this view, emotions, which are considered to be a part of an older brain structure, can be regulated through cognition (MacLean, 1990). However, the scientific community has known for decades that this theory is inaccurate. For a more up to date model of neural evolution see Cesario *et al.*, 2020. The classical view of emotions goes hand in hand with the triune model of the brain, and practice guided by these theories might not always be in the best interest of its beneficiaries. By knowing about

allostasis as the “body budget” and about emotions as whole-brain processes, the same as others (e.g. thinking) psychologists could integrate into their practice, besides work with the thoughts and the emotions of the clients, guidance towards improving sleep, exercising and adopting a healthy diet as ways of improving the “body budget” and, as a result, feeling better and more energetic to live fulfilled lives (Tabibnia & Radecki, 2018).

Another contribution that the constructivist theory can bring to psychotherapy is the concept of emotional granularity. As people learn very specific emotion labels, they can have enriched emotional experiences and they can help regulate the body’s energy needs (Barrett, 2017c; Tugade *et al.*, 2004). In a study comparing the effects of affect-labeling, reappraisal, distraction from the feared stimulus (a spider), and exposure alone, the affect-labeling group showed reduced skin conductance response compared to the other groups, even though they did not differ in self-report fear. Greater use of fear and anxiety words during exposure was associated with greater fear responding reductions (Kircanski, Liberman & Craske, 2012).

DISCUSSION

The classical view of emotions is still very popular and embedded into child-rearing, education, autism interventions, and psychotherapy, to name just a few domains. This view posits that there are a few basic emotions that are “natural kinds” and that have specific fingerprints (neural circuitry, facial expressions and so on). However, the scientific evidence is gathering in favor of the constructivist approach of emotions (Siegel *et al.*, 2018; Kober *et al.*, 2008). According to this view, instances of the same emotion (e.g. fear) can vary greatly and no fingerprint can consistently be found in any of the areas indicated by the classical view. An important distinction is made between emotions and affect. Affect is a state that accompanies consciousness throughout life and it has two dimensions: arousal (high-low) and valence (pleasant-unpleasant). Emotions are viewed as concepts, acquired through language, not essences, they are “made” in the brain in the same way as other mental events (e.g. thoughts). Constructing emotions serves a function for allostasis – the process of predictively managing energy needs.

Parents, teachers, professionals working with people with autism spectrum condition (ASC), and psychotherapists could benefit from understanding the new science of emotion. One important benefit is the knowledge that we are not at the “mercy” of our emotions and that we can take responsibility in constructing an emotional experience that is in our best interest. Also, we could pay more attention to our lifestyle (exercise, sleep, diet) in order to have more positive emotions and more energy. Another practical implication would be to teach and practice emotional granularity to regulate our affective states.

Like all scientific theories, the theory of constructed emotion has its limitations. Many of its assumptions are based on the current understanding of how the brain works, but some assumptions go beyond the evidence. More research is necessary to either confirm these hypotheses or to disprove them and replace them with more accurate ones.

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